

THE SIGNIFICANCE OF DEBATES FOR ENHANCING SPEAKING SKILLS

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Annotation. *This article discusses the significance of debates during the classes and shows the ways how to organize it efficiently.*

Key words: *explicit instruction, expected argument, technique, literacy, contextualized, technique.*

Аннотация. *В данной статье рассматривается значение дебатов во время занятий и показаны способы их эффективной организации.*

Ключевые слова: *явная инструкция, ожидаемый аргумент, техника, грамотность, контекстуализация, методика.*

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu maqola dars davomida bahs-munozaralarning ahamiyatini ko'rib chiqadi va ularni qanday qilib samarali tashkil etishni ko'rsatadi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *aniq ko'rsatma, kutilayotgan dalil, texnika, savodxonlik, kontekstualizatsiya, metodologiya.*

Debate is an excellent activity for language learning because it engages students in a variety of cognitive and linguistic ways. In addition to providing meaningful listening, speaking and writing practice, debate is also highly effective for developing argumentation skills for persuasive speech and writing. There are several methods that are used by teachers for teaching speaking. The method should be interesting to involve the students in teaching the learning process. One of the teaching methods in improving speaking is a debate. John F. Kennedy told: "I think debating in high school and college is most valuable training whether for politics, the law, business, or for service on community committees such as the PTA and the League of Women Voters"¹. A good debater must not only study material in support of his own case, but he must also thoroughly analyze the expected argument of his opponent.

The give and take of debating, the testing of ideas, is essential to democracy. I wish we had a good deal more debating in our educational institutions than we do now. It means that debates are very beneficial in any field and extremely important to be practiced with the whole population in order to teach people to speak properly and to express their thoughts and ideas in a clear, comprehensible way. Debate is an excellent activity for language learning because it engages students in a variety of cognitive and linguistic ways. In addition to providing meaningful listening, speaking and writing practice, debate is also highly effective for developing argumentation skills for persuasive speech and writing. According to Penny Ur debate is anything from the simplest question-answer guessing process to the most complex political and philosophical debates. Mostly debate in a foreign language is used to practice efficient fluency but it is not the only aim of the debates. Language is never used for its own

¹ John F. Kennedy. August 22, 1960. "Public speech".

sake; it is used to persuade, inform, threaten, and inquire and to achieve an objective². Achieving an objective should be one of the aims in order to hold the debate. The purpose of the debate is important to be taken very intensely and the results respected by teachers and students. It is known that in many debates there is much to be learnt from what is said. Debates also can teach to generalize from the given examples, to draw analogies, to judge priorities and infer reasons.

Debating skills include not only speaking but also listening to what was said, not interrupting and explaining your point of view in clear and relevant way. A debate that works is that in which as many students as possible say as much as possible.

Two crucial components of successful debate are high motivation and full participation of students. Debate works when the language is used in a variable ways in terms of communication and subject matter functions. Taking part in a debate helps young people to construct logical arguments for and against specific issues.

They begin to realize that the information and knowledge they have received earlier has a practical purpose. The most remarkable point in debating is to bring fresh evidences, suggest original examples, and think of cogent point³.

Debates can develop discussion skills of students through the following steps: balanced participation of all the members of the group; prohibition of interruptions, correct turn taking; keeping voices down so as not to disturb other groups. Before starting the debates there are four steps to be covered Read for background information about the subject: Prepare a comprehensive bibliography. Collect as much material as you can find. Read and study the material discovered.

While conducting a debate it is extremely important to focus on learning that means the learning should be process oriented. For example, the way the debates are conducted is simplified to just dividing the students into groups and giving the statement. This is traditional way of conducting debates and it leaks the process of preparation that influence the loss or even absence of drilling the skills that debates should develop. The debates in our practice are just a discussion where students are just exchanging their opinions. Usually teachers give the topic and few minutes to think on that topic, and then ask students to discuss. Nevertheless, students are not being able to search for the information, which is the extremely important part in debates. That means that they are not just changing and simplifying the rules of debates, but also not practicing the research skills of students.

There are several techniques and strategies which are used by the teacher for teaching speaking. The technique or strategy should be interesting to interest students in teaching learning process. One of the teaching strategies in teaching speaking is debate strategy. It is seen as an active learning process because students will learn more through a process constructing and creating, working in a group and also sharing knowledge. Thus, debate is an excellent activity for language learning because it

² Penny Ur, A course in language teaching, 1991 Cambridge university press.

³ Ram Avtar Tyagi, Effective Methods of Teaching English, New Delhi: Alpha Publications, 2006, pp. 178-179.

engages students in a variety of cognitive and linguistic ways⁴. Debate can motivate students thinking, moreover, if they must defend their stand or opinion which is in contradiction with conviction them. This strategy can involve all students to be active, not only the debate performer. Competitive debating uses the skills of argument to debate and discuss important issues about our beliefs, government policies and proposals on how to improve the world or face up to problems in society.

A competitive debate should be rational, focused, and structured. Nevertheless, debating builds a unique set of skills, helping students to analyze problems, think critically, synthesize arguments and present these ideas in a cogent and convincing manner. Debate can be implemented as the alternative way to teach speaking. Debate is different from other strategies. In debate, students are given some topics to be discussed. One or two students would present their opinions and facts concerning the topics. The next step, they response to the students questions and comments.

Having many chances to train and practice with students to participate in English debate competitions, the researcher found that debate was a challenging and highly rewarding activity for those who were involved. It has been argued that debate allows students to share and cooperate with one another. It educates students with responsibility, encourages creativity, deepens friendships and strengthens the rapport with the teacher. Learners need to know how speakers differ from one another and how particular circumstances call for different forms of speech. They can learn how speaking styles affect listeners. Thus, the rate at which they speak, the volume and the precision of pronunciation may differ substantially from one situation to another. It is useful for students to know that speech should differ informality, such as when speaking to a judge, a teacher, a parent or a playmate. They may also benefit from learning about the differences among various dialects.

The subjects in the curriculum and examples from the media may provide occasions for different forms of speech. Oral presentations can be derived from poems, stories, newspaper and magazine articles, as well scientific reports. Dramatic acting and watching skits and plays may provide the richest opportunity to see how character and circumstance affect speech. Students, adolescents and adult sometimes fear the challenge of sustained, formal speaking before large groups. Teachers can help reduce unrealistic fears by pointing out how common they are among people and what to do about them. They can also help to reduce such fears by maintaining a friendly atmosphere in the class and providing opportunities for students to practice alone or with one other student and then before increasingly larger groups. Thus, students can practice speaking in front of their peers who face the same situation. Students can practice presenting information and questions and holding group discussions. Frequent classroom presentations discussions enable teachers to diagnose and remedy problems. Students can benefit from learning by setting themselves presentation goals and assessing their own progress. Observing proficient speakers can help students to set such goals. Practicing oral presentation in these ways can lessen students' anxieties while, at the same time, helping them to learn the subject matter of the lesson. The

⁴ Brown, G., Yule, G. 1991. Teaching Spoken Language. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, p 87

ability to speak freely also improves when students practice debate because they take part in conversations as they are debating. Likewise, debate can motivate student to practice the language. It can embolden students in critical thinking, and develop students' speaking ability in communication. Most importantly, debate offers an opportunity for students to move beyond the acquisition of basic knowledge in a subject matter and progress into the types of higher order critical thinking skills that good debate requires. Debaters must analyze, synthesize and evaluate the knowledge they have acquired in order to propose, oppose and make competing choices. Debaters apply course material through the use of well-reasoned arguments that are capable of being understood by not only their professor but also their peers. This process develops and improves oral communication skills, and at the same time, hones students' listening skills as a necessity to make effective rebuttals. The groups in each corner of the classroom comes work together to come up with the best arguments for their position. After a specified time for group discussion, each group presents their strongest arguments to the other groups. This can be made in presentation form or through a more directed debate where the professor or assigned students can moderate and direct time for each group to present and rebut. After the debate, students are permitted to switch sides if their personal views changed. This form of debate directly counters the argument of dualism, showing there are more than two-sides to an issue, and often, variations of the sides. Role-play debates also help to avoid dualistic debate models by assigning students to argue on behalf of different characters in a situation. For instance, in the issue of national health care, students could be assigned to various roles, such as doctor, patient, a wealthy person, a poor person, a lawyer, a judge, an insurance company, the president, and so on. Through the debate of the issue from various points of view, the students can broaden their understanding of the issue and its complexity. Fishbowl debates can take several different forms, but usually involve grouping chairs in a circle pattern. Several chairs are then placed inside the circle for teams representing the different positions of the debate. Chairs can also be added for several students representing the audience. To bolster attention among those outside the fishbowl, an empty chair can be added, which is free game, allowing someone from the outside to enter the fishbowl to ask a question or make an argument. Think-pair-share debates require students to think and make notes alone about the issue. After personal reflection is completed, pairs are formed. The pairs then work together, comparing their notes and creating lists to support both sides of the issue. Once complete, the pairs of two are combined with another pair. The newly formed groups of four discuss the issue, choose, a position, and edit their list down to their best arguments.

In conclusion, we can say that debate is one of the effective ways of improving speaking skills, furthermore language skills will improve because students are using language for specific purposes and working toward personal goals. Students develop research skills and synthesize information. Debate empowers students as they make decisions about their learning and display their knowledge in meaningful ways.

References:

1. Brown, G., Yule, G. 1991. Teaching Spoken Language. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
2. Ram Avtar Tyagi, Effective Methods of Teaching English, New Delhi: Alpha Publications, 2006, pp. 178-179.
3. John F. Kennedy. August 22, 1960. "Public speech".
4. Penny Ur, A course in language teaching, 1991 Cambridge university press.
5. Yuliani, Fatimah. 2009. The Implementation of Debate in Teaching Speaking to the First Year Students of RSBI: Muhammadiyah University of Suarakarta.